

ETHNO-RELIGIOUS CONFLICTS AND THE RISING LOSS OF LIVES IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

Christiana Aniedi Stephen

Directorate of Public Order and Information Management

Faculty of Social Sciences

University of Uyo, Uyo

ABSTRACT

This work was undertaken to assess the Impacts of Ethno-religious Conflicts on Rising Killings in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The researcher made use of Parson's Structural Conflict for the theoretical framework. Survey research design was adopted by the researcher. Three research objectives were adopted from which three Hypotheses were formulated. The sample for this study after calculation was 400 but the returned questionnaires were 393 which formed the basis for the sample size. Study participants were aged between 18 to 50 years and above, who were randomly selected from Sabo, Kakuri, Kawo and Angwa Sariki communities between the geo-division of Kaduna State into Kaduna North and South. Sabo and Kakuri were chosen from the south while Kaow and Agwa Sariki were chosen from the north. Data were collected through the use of both a questionnaire and an interview schedule. Quantitative data were analysed with Pearson product-moment correlation (r) with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) while the qualitative data were analysed thematically with excerpts. Socio-demographic data were presented and analysed using simple percentages. The findings of the study revealed that Ethno-religious conflict is a causal factor for the killings of people in Kaduna State. This was confirmed by the results of the tested hypothesis which indicated a strong significant relationship between the variables and the narratives from interviewees. Among others, the researcher recommends legislation, advocacy and sensitization of the Kaduna people and the government on the cost of Ethno-religious conflicts on the lives, properties and well-being of the people of the state.

KEYWORDS: Conflicts, Ethno-religious Conflicts, Killing, Loss of Lives, and Kaduna

INTRODUCTION

According to Chidi (2023), ethno-religious conflicts arise from actual or imagined differences rooted in ethnic and religious identities, lineages, and perspectives. Conflicts involving religious groups where religion is an integral part of social and cultural life, and where religious institutions are representative, morally valid, or have mobilisation potential are considered ethno-religious. When conflicting groups are defined along ethno-religious lines and perspectives, religious identity, it can create clear differences between the parties and increase the mobilisation of the group.

Ethno-religious conflicts when often lead to destabilization at different levels, from countries to states and local government areas, especially in Africa (Daniel and Bako, 2023). These conflicts are accompanied by serious violations of human rights, including genocide and crimes against humanity. In addition, they contribute to economic decline, state fragility, environmental problems and the displacement of the population as refugees. The consequences of violent ethnic conflicts are marked by loss of life, great human suffering and considerable destruction of property. According to Egwu (2022), ethno-religious conflict is a form of conflict that is said to arise from real or imagined "differences" rooted in ethnic and religious identities. It is "assumed" because of the need to avoid the essentialism that characterizes discourses on identity politics, especially the independent power attributed to these identities in the formation of political consciousness. The notion of ethno-religious identity arises from the congruence and mutually reinforcing relationship between ethnic identities. Religious practices play a significant role in social and political processes. As the situation has been well described, religious identity sometimes becomes part of the identity of an ethnic group or vice versa and represents an unstable social mix accompanied by the power of the myth of the ethnic group.

National security is understood as the absence of danger or threats to the ability of a nation to defend and develop itself or to promote its legitimate interests and improve the well-being of its citizens. According to Nnoli (2006), national security has an "objective" and "subjective" dimension: the first is measured by the lack of threat, anxiety or danger, while the second is measured by the lack of fear of threat, anxiety or the risk materializes. However, despite what seems to be the inclusiveness implied in this definition with an emphasis on the well-being of citizens, the traditional national security literature takes as its starting point the framework of defense and strategic doctrine so that national security is reduced to state security and the narrow interests of the elite in power. National security then becomes a state of peace decided by the elite at the traditional community level, the state level, and the national level (Peters and Bassey, 2019).

The place of public order is the act of upholding the peaceful setting of the public law in its traditional setting to enhance humans' existence and activities within a pace of harmonization of available resources toward the success of society in the absence of conflict. According to Peters and Bassey (2019), order within society lies within the elite class who can direct the lower class or workers. They further maintained that a shift in public order is the creation of a path for conflict which is mostly led or caused by the custodians of codes of order, customs and acceptable boundary limits. Ethno-religious conflicts have been a result of a shift in the public order from the perspectives of religious ideological differences originating from the elite class and spreading across the various lower classes of the populace.

Nigeria is beleaguered by violent conflict arising from ethnicity and religious issues in the northern states (Okpanachi, 2010; Krause, 2011; Alimba, 2014; Mustapha, 2014). Ethno-religious polarization and conflicts in Nigeria have intensified in recent years due to the politics of religion and ethnic values (Chidi, 2023). This has led to an increase in the savagery and rate of destruction of life and property, as well as tensions between Nigeria's various ethnic and religious groups. Among the effects of these conflicts are an increased proliferation of weapons by various groups, armed banditry and kidnappings. The scale and prevalence of these conflicts in Nigeria remain a matter of concern and require urgent attention from all stakeholders. As a result of these conflicts, Nigeria's social, economic and political progress has suffered, threatening national security (Chidi, 2023).

Daniel and Bako (2023) posit that ethno-religious conflicts pose a major security challenge in the world, with Nigeria particularly affected. According to the work of Iruonagbe and George (2007), Nigeria is plagued by ongoing conflicts and security challenges, stemming mainly from social, ethnic, cultural and religious differences. These challenges are compounded by deep inequalities in the distribution of power, wealth and resources, creating an environment where resistance to the prevailing status quo becomes inevitable. Ethno-religious conflicts often lead to destabilization at different levels, from countries to states and local communities, especially in Africa. These conflicts are accompanied by serious violations of human rights, including genocide and crimes against humanity. Works of literature like Egwu (2022); Chidi (2023) and Iruonagbe and George (2007) have revealed the rising of ethno-religious conflict in Nigeria and its corresponding consequences. The northern part and the middle belt of Nigeria have recently become a more experienced region in this conflict (Egwu, 2022). Within existing literature, the impact of this conflict in Kaduna State as a set of literature has not been captured which is the identifiable gap in the literature that this work seeks to fill. Against this backdrop, this research seeks to assess the impact of ethno-religious conflict on national security and public order from the Kaduna State experiences.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Some research has shown that ethnic and religious conflicts have had a serious and negative impact on the socio-economic and political development of Nigeria (Iruonagbe and George, 2007; Lamorde, 2018; Salawu, 2010; Egwu, 2022; Chidi, 2023; Daniel and Bako, 2023). These conflicts have negative effects on the national security, stability and integration of the country (Amusan, 2001). The manipulation of religion and ethnicity by religious and ethnic leaders has been a significant obstacle in the country's efforts to reach greater heights. Ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria have become major boundaries that create divisions among people. Ethnicity and religion have also become tools of mobilization and manipulation in Nigeria (Agbiboa, 2013). Ethnic and religious conflicts are common and pose significant security challenges in Nigeria. The long-standing ethno-religious conflict leads to the destruction of human life and property. As a result, the conflicts have left many injured and many thousands of people displaced from their homelands. In other words, the ethno-religious strife led to the loss of human life and capital; that is why this document is worth reviewing.

Kaduna today is divided into two major areas: the predominantly Christian south and

the predominantly Muslim north, whose residents have been unjustifiably exploited to fuel ethno-religious conflicts (Ogbahi, 2017). Kaduna, once a relatively peaceful city, has experienced a cycle of violence, making it one of the most volatile cities in northern Nigeria (Makar, 2004). Until now, the two dominant religions - Christianity and Islam - have had opposing relations in the socio-economic and political affairs of the state, which further shows that the subsequent unrest in Kaduna State, often identified as ethno-religious conflicts from 1980 to date, has political, social, ethnic and religious overtones and have resulted in the loss of lives and property worth millions of naira in many cities and towns across the country (Ogbahi, 2017).

The Kafanchan riots of March 1987 began with theological disputes between Christian and Muslim students at the Kafanchan Teachers College, Kafanchan, in Jema'a Emirate, south of Zaria (Suberu, 1996). These disputes quickly turned into a clash that spread in the city of Kafanchan and ignited centuries-old tensions between the politically dominant Hausa-Fulani Muslim settlers located in the centre of the city, on the one hand, and the minority settlers, predominantly Christians and/or the indigenous non-Hausa-Fulani animists living on the outskirts of the city, instead. According to a source, "the natives of Kafanchan were unhappy with the Hausa rule because it deprived them of their wealth and power, making them practically strangers in their land" (Sunday New Nigerian, 15 March 1987: 1). Indeed, the intensity of the opposition of this ethnic minority to the dominance of the emirate was shown by the angry opposition and physical attacks carried out by indigenous Kafanchan elements on the Emir of Jema'a, Alhaji Isa Muhammadu, when he tried to intervene in the Kafanchan College of Education (New Sunday Nigeria, 15 March 1987: 1). However, the worst phase of the Kafanchan crisis occurred in areas such as the city of Kaduna, Katsina and Funtua, where Muslim mobs attacked Christian communities and/or migrants from the south of Nigeria and their properties (mainly churches and hotels) in retaliation for the murder of Muslims and the burning of mosques in the city of Kafanchan.

Religious crises continue in Kaduna with the Zango Kataf crisis in February and mid-May 1992. According to Uroko (2018), Edward John of the International Research Group for Transregional Studies and Emergencies reported that during the Zango Kataf ethno-religious conflict, a dusk-to-dawn curfew was imposed in Kaduna State in May 1992. On the 19th, after two days of what reports described as religious clashes that left up to 100 dead, caused by the rioters who marched through the streets, looting and burning at will, the general hospital was shot down with the wounded. This conflict has divided Kaduna State along religious lines. A mistrust arose between the different believers of the state. Muslim and Christian neighbourhoods emerged in Kaduna. These conflicts have repeated over and over again through the Sharia crisis of 2000 and the Miss World crisis of 2002. This crisis has led to hundreds of lives being lost and continues to be lost due to religious crises in Kaduna State. Works of literature like Suberu (1996); Makar, (2004); Ogbahi, (2017); Uroko (2018) have concentrated on the causes, trends and strategies to control Ethno-religious conflict in Kaduna leaving the gap in the impacts of Ethno-religious conflicts on killings in Kaduna State. Against this backdrop, this work seeks to assess the impact of Ethno-religious conflict on the loss of lives in Kaduna State.

HYPOTHESIS

- i. H_0 : there is no significant relationship between Ethno-religious conflict and the rising loss of life among the people of Kaduna State

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Structural Conflict Theory

Many theories offer a theoretical explanation of why conflicts arise apart from the main Conflict Theory as propounded by Karl Marx. In their efforts to explain the nature, causes and effects of events in their society, social scientists have always developed theories. To analyse the contextual variables of this study, the theoretical framework adopted for this study is structural conflict theory.

Structural conflict theory provides an adequate explanation, a predictive justification for the frequent occurrence of ethno-religious conflicts and the tendency to offer them a summary of the ways to solve problems that arise from these conflicts (Alao, 2015). According to Ogbahi (2017) Parson in 1960, an American sociologist, favours the development of this theory after the Second World War. In this theory, he thought that "individuals adapt to a certain structure in an organisation, institution or society. Any change in the structure of the organization or institution causes conflict and destabilizes society." The structural conflict theory includes two branches, radical structuralists and liberal structuralists. According to Faleti (2006), radical structuralism comes mainly from the Marxist dialectical school, including figures such as Marx, Engels and Lenin. Liberal structuralists include Ross (1993), Scarborough (1998) and Galtung (1990).

The main argument of structural theory is that social conflicts arise because of how societies are structured and organised. The theory considers social problems such as political and economic exclusion, injustice, poverty, exploitation and inequality as sources of conflict (Faleti, 2006). This theory is heavily based on the Marxist theory of historical materialism. Conflict is a common occurrence in societies where one class dominates another due to an exploitative and unjust system, according to the structuralist perspective. The liberal structuralist calls for the elimination of structural defects through new policies with a human face (Chidi, 2023).

The Rationale for Adopting Structural Conflict Theory

Structural Conflict Theory proposes that social conflicts arise because of the way societies are structured and organized. This makes the theory more suitable for the study based on the fact that the Kaduna society is structured along ethnic plurality and multi-religious affiliations. This structure has a form of conflict within the system of the structure based on the existing differences which is embedded in the structure. The plurality of ethnic groups presents cultural differences in which religion is an important element of culture.

The presence of Muslims and Christians within the existing structure of the Kaduna society presents a state with groups of people living with opposing religious ideological beliefs. These differences which the people are attached to form the basis of conflicts which in due time manifest into violent conflicts that involve cool blood murders, the burning down of religious buildings, houses and other people's properties. These violent activities within the structural setting of Kaduna State have given credence to Parson's Structural Conflict Theory.

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was adopted for the study. This research design has exploratory, investigative, and explanatory potentials to make it easier for the collection of information and to address substantive issues raised in the research objectives which enhanced testing of the hypothesis of the study and the thematic analysis of the interviews' narratives. This type of research design provides for multiple qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques and analysis. A questionnaire and interview schedule were used to provide a convenient tool for the collection of primary data for analysis in the study.

The study was conducted in Kaduna State. Kaduna is a state in the North West geopolitical zone of Nigeria. According to Iniobong (2016), Kaduna is the capital of the Northern Region and is a state with a diverse cultural and ethnic heritage. The major ethnic groups consist of Fulani, Hausa, Bajju, Jaba, Adara, Moro'a, Gbagyi, Gure, Kurama, Numana, and Ninzo, as well as Kataf, Koro, and Atyap, among others. The name Kaduna comes from the Hausa word "Kada," which means crocodile, and "Kaduna" is the Hausa plural for crocodiles, many of which are abundant in the Kaduna River. The state capital is the city of Kaduna, which was the 8th largest city in the country in 2006. Established in 1967 as North Central State, which also includes modern Katsina State, Kaduna State took its current boundaries in 1987 (Yusuf, 2015). Kaduna State is the fourth largest and third most populous in the country. According to the City Population, the population of Kaduna State as of 2022 was 9,032,200. This population figure consists of the population statistics of all the state's local government areas. The population is based on the projection of the annual percentage of the 2006 National Population Commission figure. Hence, the sample size of this study was 400 and were randomly selected from the chosen areas.

The sample for this study was adults aged between 18 and 50 years, who were randomly selected from Sabo, Kakuri in Southern Kaduna and from Kawo and Angwa Sariki from Northern Kaduna. Kaduna State was divided by the existing geo-political divides of Northern Kaduna and Southern Kaduna. Four (4) communities were randomly selected within the clusters in both Kaduna South and Kaduna North based on their homogeneous characteristics. Two (2) communities were selected from each cluster. A simple random sampling method was adopted by the researcher to select study participants from each of the selected communities. The North is mostly Muslims and the South is mostly Christians. Hence, the sample size of this study was 400 and were randomly selected from the chosen areas.

RESULT

H_0 : there is no significant relationship between Ethno-religious conflict and the rising loss of life among the people of Kaduna State

Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used for testing hypothesis 1 which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between Ethno-religious conflict (ERC) and the rising loss of life (RLL) among the people of Kaduna State as presented in the table below.

Table 1: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Ethno-religious conflict (ERC) and rising loss of life (RLL) in Kaduna State

Correlation between Ethno-religious Conflict (ERC) and Rising Loss of Life (RLL) (n = 393)

		ERC	RLL
ERC	Pearson Correlation	1	.891**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	393	393
RLL	Pearson Correlation	.891**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	393	393

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that the Pearson product-moment correlation between Ethno-religious conflict (ERC) and the rising loss of life (RLL) among the people of Kaduna State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.891, p < 0.001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis one was not supported. This implies that there is a significant relationship between Ethno-religious conflict (ERC) and the rising loss of life (RLL) among the people of Kaduna State. The implication here is that ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State are always accompanied by loss of lives in Kaduna State. Therefore, Ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State have contributed to a high death toll within the state. The high positive relationship between the study variables as captured in Hypothesis 1 is indicated by the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) which is $+0.891$. The rules state that there exists a high positive or negative correlation when $r = \pm 0.70$ to ± 0.90 . In the case of the correlation (r) between Ethno-religious conflict (ERC) and the rising loss of life (RLL) among the people of Kaduna State, the Pearson Product-moment Correlation $r = +0.891$ which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables and the statistical significant is lower than 0.01 level of significant at .000.

Ethno-religious Conflict and Rising Loss of Life

Data gathered through interviews with the study participants showed that Ethno-religious conflict is responsible for more loss of life than any other death factor among the people of Kaduna State. Reports from narratives given by the participants revealed that a lot of people have been murdered in Kaduna State through Ethno-religious conflicts, and many corpses have not been counted to date. Participants lamented the rising loss of lives through Ethno-religious conflicts in the state and the inability of the state government and the federal government to provide security for lives and properties for the people of Kaduna State. A study participant, during an interview, reported that;

We are tired of burying our people every time in Kaduna. We

have lost so many of our sons and daughters to this religious conflicts in Kaduna that we cannot account anymore for our dead who died during these crises. This conflicts have brought about so many deaths in this state than motor accidents every year. Now it is every year and this bandits are bringing us more crises and death. The pain is that our government is not doing what they supposed to do about this (female, aged 50 years, interviewed on 17th July 2024 at Sabo).

Another participant had this to say on the killings in Kaduna State;

There is no crises in Kaduna that we do not loss people. The point I do not understand is that the way we kill ourselves is so bad that after the conflict I will be surprised as we the Muslims will sell to Christians who come to buy from us and the Christians will sell to us and we will live as if we didn't kill each other. This makes these crises so foolish that I am still wondering why there should be these conflicts (male, aged 32 years, interviewed on 17th July 2024 at Kawo)

Data retrieved from the field through interviews on Ethno-religious conflicts and the rising loss of lives in Kaduna unveiled that the majority of the study participants thought that people are murdered in cool blood in Kaduna State during Ethno-religious conflicts which occur more and now more often in the state. Narratives revealed that Kaduna State has a history of loss of lives to Ethno-religious conflicts and this has brought about a reduction in population and mass movement of the non-northerners from the state. These killings have cost a lot of families their breadwinners, parents and progenitors of families thereby bringing a great loss to many families in the state.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study on hypothesis one of the research work show that there exists a high relationship between Ethno-religious conflict and rising loss of lives among the people of Kaduna State. This was ascertained by the Pearson product Moment Correlation ($r = +0.891$, $p < 0.001$ significance level) between the two study variables. The finding showed that ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State are always accompanied by loss of lives in Kaduna State. Ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State have contributed to a high death toll within the state. Findings also revealed that a lot of people have been murdered in Kaduna State through Ethno-religious conflicts, and many corpses have not been counted to date. The emergence of findings revealed that the majority of the study participants thought that people were murdered in cool blood in Kaduna State during Ethno-religious conflicts which occur more and now more often in the state. According to findings, these killings have cost a lot of families their breadwinners, parents and progenitors of families thereby bringing a great loss to many families in the state. Further findings have shown that the violent clashes between the Muslims and Christians in Kaduna State have taken several people to their untimely graves mostly in blood murder during these crises.

This finding agrees with Zwahu (2012) who explained that during the Ethno-religious conflicts of 2000 and 2002, and ethnic clashes in Kaduna State, the residents of southern

Kaduna were killed, beaten and maimed, and Human Rights Watch describes this as the worst outbreak of violence in Nigeria since the 1967-1970 civil war. These findings also agree with Salawu (2010) who further reported that in September 2001, ethnic tensions between the Tivs and Iunkuns in Plateau State and the ripples in Kaduna State reached a fever pitch after decades of fighting. The ethnic tension of September 2001 in Jos was caused by what can be called mistaken identity. This means that the Tiv mistook nineteen soldiers for Iunkuns, but dressed in fake military uniforms. The Tiv youths caught them and slaughtered them one by one. The reaction of the people led to the loss of lives in Jos and the ripples were all over other states of the north including Kaduna State.

CONCLUSION

Kaduna State has been a known state for Ethno-conflict conflicts from the Zango-kataf conflict to the Sharia crises to Miss World beauty pageant conflicts, and the recent herdsmen and farmers clashes. Ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State are always accompanied by loss of lives in Kaduna State. Ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna State have contributed to a high death toll within the state. These killings have cost a lot of families their breadwinners, parents and progenitors of families thereby bringing a great loss to many families in the state. Further findings have shown that the violent clashes between the Muslims and Christians in Kaduna State have taken several people to their untimely graves mostly in blood murder during these crises.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made by the researcher from the findings of the study:

1. The people of Kaduna State should be made to understand the cost of ethnic and religious conflicts in terms of loss of life by the National and State Orientation.
2. The government should educate the people of Kaduna State on the cost implications of conflicts and work on modalities for peaceful co-existence between the Muslims and Christians living in the state.

REFERENCES

- Agbiboa, D. E. (2013). Ethno-religious conflicts and the elusive quest for national identity in Nigeria. *Journal of Black Studies*, 44(1), 3-30.
- Alao, D. O. (2015). Issues in Conflict, Peace and Governance. [Leiden University catalogue](#).
- Alimba, N. C. (2014). Probing the dynamic of communal conflict in Northern Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 8(1), 177-204.
- Amusan, L. (2001). Ethno-religious and environmental conflicts: challenges to human security and development in Nigeria. *Perspectives*, (16), 57-68.
- Chidi, S. O. (2023). Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Nigeria (2015-2021): Implications for National Security. Retrieved online as PDF file on 17th July 2024. *NIJPCR* 2(2): 263 – 279
- Daniel, R. O. and Bako, A. (2023). Ethno-Religious Conflict: A Threat to Benevolent Intergroup Relations in Wukari Metropolis, Taraba State, Nigeria. *Wukari International Studies Journal*, Vol 7 (3): 178 – 199

- Faleti, S.A. (2006) *Theories of Social Conflict*. Spectrum Books Limited, Ibadan.
- Galtung, J. (1990). Cultural Violence. *Journal of Peace Research*, 27(3) p. 292
- Iniobong, M. (2016). *Kaduna State – The Main Capital City in the Northern Region*. Retrieved from <https://www.hotelnownow.com/blog/kaduna-state/> on the 10th July 2024
- Iruonagbe, T. C and George, T. (2007). Conflicts and Intergroup Relation in Nigeria What Way Forward. *Journal of Arts and Education*. 2(2): 17 -32.
- Krause, J. (2011). A deadly cycle: Ethno-religious conflict in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. Working Paper. Switzerland: Geneva Declaration. 34
- Lamorde, Z. (2018). Managing ethno-religious identity conflicts in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 23(9), 51-57.
- Mustapha, A. R. (2014). *Sects & Social Disorder: Muslim identities & conflict in Northern Nigeria (Vol. 5)*. Boydell & Brewer Ltd.
- New Nigerian, 17 April 1987: 9. *Kafanchan Crises*.
- Nnoli, O. (2006). *National Security in Africa: A Radical New Perspective*. Pan African Centre for Research on Peace and Conflict Resolution (PACREP), Enugu, Nigeria. 139
- Ogbahi, E. P. (2017). Conflicts in Southern Kaduna: Causes and Strategies for Resolution. *JORAS* 12(7): 12-28
- Okpanachi, E. (2010). Ethno-religious identity and conflict in northern Nigeria: understanding the dynamics of sharia in Kaduna and Kebbi states. IFRA-Nigeria e-Papers, (07)
- Peters, M. I. and Aniekan E. Bassey (2019). Complicating Social Order in the Rural Areas of Akwa Ibom State. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. Volume 17 Number, 2: 112 – 125
- Ross, M. (1993). *The Management of Conflict: Interpretations and Interests in Comparative Perspective*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Salawu, B. (2010). Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Nigeria: Causal Analysis and Proposals for New Management Strategies. *European Journal of Social Sciences* 13(3): 345 -353
- Scarborough, G. I. (1998). “An Expert system for Assessing Vulnerability to Instability.” In J. Davies & T.R. Gur (Eds). (1998), *Preventive Measures: Building Risk Assessment and Crisis Early Warning Systems*. Lanham MD: Rowan and Littlefield.
- Suberu, R. T. (1996). *Ethnic Minority Conflicts and Governance in Nigeria (1–)*. IFRA-Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.ifra.748>
- Sunday New Nigerian, 15 March 1987:1. *Kafanchan Crises*.
- Uroko, F. C. (2018). The Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Southern Kaduna of Nigeria: Causes and Implications for National Development. *Afro-Asian Journal of Social Sciences* 9(2): 1 – 12.
- Wapwera, S. D. and Gajere, J. K. (2017). Ethno-religious Urban Violence and Residential Mobility in Nigerian Cities: The Kaduna Experience. *Hindawi Urban Studies Research*. Volume 2017, Article ID 4624768, 10 pages.
- Yusuf, S. (2015). *Kaduna: Physical and Human Environment*. Retrieved online as PDF file on 13th July 2024.